

Indonesian pre-service teachers' mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement

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ABSTRACT

Pre-service teachers must be able to fulfill the standards of having teachers' competencies and more than adequate knowledge to teach the future generations. In relation to this, mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic ability become crucial reasons they need in perceiving the quality to become professional teachers. The respondents of this study were 68 students who were English as a Foreign Language (EFL) pre-service teachers ranging from the age of 19-22 from the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education at one of the university in South Sumatra, Indonesia. The aims of this study were to find out the relationship among these pre-service teachers' mindfulness, social emotional competence and academic achievement. The instruments of this study were the five-facet mindfulness and social emotional competence questionnaires. The documentation of their GPA which were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Test. The results of this study showed that pre-service teachers had high level of mindfulness and social emotional competence. It also highlighted that there were significant weak correlation between their five facet mindfulness and academic achievement, and their five facet mindfulness and social emotional competence toward academic achievement. Specifically, the non-judging dimension from the five-facet mindfulness and self-management from social emotional competence also correlated significantly to academic achievements. In conclusion, the pre-service teachers' mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement had beneficial relationship one another.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the important elements playing the most crucial role in the development of education is teachers. Teachers play most crucial role in the development of the education system as a whole and also in imparting and maintaining the standards of higher education [1]. It means the development of good education is also based on the quality of the teachers. Since teachers play this very important role, Indonesia requires her teachers to be professional teachers who have good standards. One of the standards that must be fulfilled by Indonesian teachers is the teachers' competencies. Teachers' competencies are the crucial factors which could contribute to the improvement of the educational system with the help of teacher training and curriculum development [2].

Based on Indonesia Law on Teacher and Lecturer no. 14, 2005, the four basic competencies required for every teacher are pedagogical, personal, professional, and social competencies. Pedagogical competence is

related to the teachers' competence in relation to collaboration, comprehensive view and contribution to the development of pedagogy for education. Teachers' personal competence refers to the ability to communicate effectively, be punctual, be discipline, and understand more about the students' characters [3]. The professional competence is the competence or skills measured by the indicators such as mastering the teaching aspects related to the curriculum, knowing the relationship between the materials with other background of materials, and mastering the ways to explore more about the teaching materials. Meanwhile, the social competence refers to the relationship between teachers and the environment or public and the ability to interact with others [4].

Among the four competencies teachers should specifically be able to maintain good personal and social competence because of their important role and their impacts to the social emotional competence of their students. Personal competence of the teachers is much more related to the personality steady, the responsibility and pride as a teacher, as well as the ability to be a role model for the students [4]. In relation to personal competence, the idea of being the role model including maintaining the relationship among the teachers, public, and students is consistently upholds. When talking about the relationship, the teachers' personal competence clearly has a link to their social competence. As one of the most important competencies needed to be acquired by teachers or pre-service teachers, the social competence is the competency dealing with the personal, peers, and group relationships. The teachers who are socially and emotionally competent are able to set the supportive relationship with the students, transfer the lesson which could enhance the students' strengths, implement the guidelines which could boost the students' intrinsic motivation, guide the students through complicated situation, encourage the students, and become the role model of pro-social behavior [5]. Teachers who have good relationship or interaction with students makes the students' level of obeying the rules and being discipline higher [6].

Moreover, pre-service teachers specifically need to obtain and keep their social emotional competence in order to be able to apply it later in their future as the professional teachers and to be able to get and maintain high academic achievement while studying in the university. Although, social-emotional learning is being integrated into pre-service teacher education course work and field experiences at the state and higher education institutional level, it is discovered that most programs and state requirements include little emphasis on social-emotional competence [7].

On the other hand, mindfulness has been spread throughout not only in psychological and medical fields but also in educational field as it has been shown to have benefits for students. Mindfulness refers to a process in noticing things, drawing distinctive idea, paying attention, and staying in the present moment [8]. Mindfulness has five dimensions, namely non-reacting to inner experiences, observing to thoughts, acting with awareness, describing or labeling with words, and non-judging of experience [9]. These five dimensions are related to the ability to maintain oneself. Mindfulness is related to the terms of self-awareness and self-management in the social emotional competence as the three aspects of social competence such as self-awareness, self-management, and social awareness skill are gained by the silence and centering mindfulness [10]. Mindfulness can also be gained by paying attention to one's everyday activities like gardening, eating, walking, listening, and school based such as class work [11].

In relation to education, mindfulness is engaged with the character education, students' awareness and attention, and social emotional learning. Mindfulness has been proven to have a good effect on the education especially for students as the students who are categorized as mindful would enhance their capability to produce a variety of solutions besides focusing on one correct answer [8]. Meanwhile, teachers could also gain the benefit from mindfulness. For example, introducing mindfulness in the teacher education is believed to enhance the character education of the pre-service teacher and job retention [12]. Another benefit like emotion regulation skill that refers to the process of reviewing, evaluating, and modifying the emotional reactions [13] could also be gained by cultivating the present moment awareness or mindfulness [14]. Thus, mindfulness is not only necessary for cultivating someone's awareness, but it goes deeper on the positive impact for education especially the students and pre-service teachers to maintain their emotion regulation skill.

In addition, one important aspect in the success of education is students' academic achievement. It has become very important in educational institution, and it has become important goals after acquiring the process of learning [15]. It is usually called as learning outcomes referring to the ability of students affected by the stimulus from the environment and cognitive process done by themselves [16]. Academic achievement or academic success is commonly measured by grades and grade point average (GPA) from the students [17]. In general, academic achievement is the results of what the students have done or have obtained after learning in an institution.

Social emotional competencies and mindfulness are two important related aspects gained by the students to support their success in academic achievement. They have already been proven to have relationship with academic achievement, which refers to the students' capability to learn and transfer their understanding or knowledge especially in the terms of the test condition [18]. Some studies claimed that mindfulness had significant relationship with academic achievement [19], [20], social emotional competencies affect students'

academic achievement [21], [22], and teachers' social emotional competence can be built through mindfulness practice [10].

Furthermore, the four factor domains of micro system, meso-system, exo-system, and macro system influence students in relation to their academic achievement [23]. Based on these factor domains, there is one contributing factor domain related to mindfulness and social emotional competence. As what has been explained previously, mindfulness and social emotional competence are related to one's ability in managing him/herself. This means, the factor domain of micro-system which involving students' resiliency, abilities, moral, and social development has relationship with both mindfulness and social emotional competence. As micro-system is one of the contributing factors influencing the academic achievement, mindfulness and social emotional competence are believed to contribute or influence students' especially pre-service teachers' academic achievement [23].

Therefore, mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement are believed to have beneficial relationship one another. Because there was no previous study involving the all three variables: mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement and the study on mindfulness and social emotional competence in Indonesian educational context is still scarce, the authors put a high interest to conduct this study that aimed to find out: i) whether or not there was any significant correlation between the pre-service teachers' mindfulness, social emotional competence and academic achievement; and ii) the highly correlated dimension of mindfulness and social emotional competency to their academic achievement.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was correlational study aimed to determine the relationship among mindfulness (X1), social emotional competence (X2), and academic achievement (Y) of the pre-service teachers who were the students of the English Education Study Program of Faculty of Teacher Training and Education in one of the university in South Sumatra, Indonesia. There were 68 respondents ranging from the age of 19-22 years served as the sample of this study which was taken by using purposive sampling technique. They were chosen because they were those in higher semester who were believed to have more experiences in acquiring the knowledge compared to the early semester students, and they had taken the same subjects and acquired the same amount of credit hours as reflected in their GPA.

In this study, the authors got the score from respondents' mindfulness and social emotional competence and documentation. The mindfulness questionnaire named Five Facet Mindfulness Questionnaire (FFMQ) consists of 39 questions [9], and the Social Emotional Competence Questionnaire (SECQ) consists of 25 questions [24]. Both questionnaires were put in Likert scale with five choices of answer for each statement. The FFMQ and SECQ were tested for the validity and reliability before given to the respondents. The results showed that there were 37 from 39 items in the FFMQ were valid, and there were 22 items in the SECQ were valid. Both questionnaires were also considered reliable as the Cronbach's Alpha of the FFMQ and SECQ were 0.839 and 0.904 respectively. Meanwhile, to get the score of respondents' academic achievement, the documentation taken from their last GPA when they were in the fifth semester was collected as the data.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis in SPSS 25 was employed to determine the correlation among mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement and to find out the contribution of each mindfulness and social emotional competence toward the academic achievement.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the respondents' five facet mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement. FFMQ was used to collect the data of the respondents' mindfulness. Since the 37 questionnaire items are in the form of Likert scale, so the ordinal data were transformed into the interval data by using the Method of Successful Intervals (MSI). The description of the information of the FFMQ result based on five categories can be seen in Table 2. The data show that there was no one achieving very low and low score of FFMQ. There are 12 respondents (17.6%) achieving medium FFMQ, 42 respondents (61.8%) achieving high FFMQ, and other 14 respondents (21.6%) achieving very high FFMQ. It can be inferred that most of the pre-service teachers had quite more than enough level of acquiring mindfulness. This indicated that these pre-service teachers were able to maintain themselves in terms of being aware and managing to stay focus in facing and solving any situation, so that basically the ability could help and enhance them to get the effective learning ability to produce their learning achievements. The students' mindfulness such as the ability to stay focus on the breathing, walking, and even becoming aware at the moment basically could give positive impact such as improving the cognitive achievements of the students [25].

Table 1. The result of five facet mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement

Variables	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Five facet mindfulness	68	106.20	166.65	1408219	15.1526
Social emotional competence	68	64.39	106.88	857778	9.2765
Academic achievement	68	2.86	3.74	3.4144	0.1559

Table 2. The results of five facet mindfulness questionnaire

Interval	Category	Frequency	Percentage
37.00–66.00	Very low	0	0%
66.01–96.00	Low	0	0%
96.01–126.00	Medium	12	17.6%
126.01–155.00	High	42	61.8%
156.01–185.00	Very high	14	21.6%

Table 3 presents the result of cumulative means of the five facet mindfulness. The pre-service teachers had highest dimension of observing ($M=32.3381$), followed by describing ($M=30.2033$), non-judging ($M=28.5940$), non-reacting ($M=27.2244$), and acting with awareness ($M=22.4621$). This shows that they had high observing and describing dimension beside other dimensions as observing and describing were two dimensions mostly acquired by college students [26]. It can be inferred that the pre-service teachers had managed to observe any situation happening to them or any activity that they had tried to do. On the other hand, they also started to express what they felt related to any situation. These are interrelated because when they were able to express or describe what they felt; it means that they had been able to observe any situation. Besides, the pre-service teachers also had enough of the other three dimensions of five facet mindfulness namely non-judging, non-reacting, and acting with awareness. It means that they were able to control themselves in terms of not easily creating any perception and addressing to any situation. Overall, the pre-service teachers' mindfulness is inferred as enough to create and enhance the effective learning activities for their achievement in learning. Mindfulness has been proved to be related to academic achievement, especially "acting with awareness" which was mostly gained by the students, and it was one of the reasons to pay attention at the present moment of activities [9].

Table 3. The cumulative means of the five-facet mindfulness

Five facet mindfulness	Mean
Observing	32.3381
Describing	30.2033
Acting with awareness	22.4621
Non-judging	28.5940
Non-reacting	27.2244

The data of the respondents' social emotional competence were collected by SECQ that consists of five competencies, namely self-awareness, social-awareness, self-management, relationship skill, and responsible decision making. Similar to the data of FFMQ the total 22 SECQ items are in the form of ordinal number, so the scores were transformed into interval data and the result can be seen in Table 4. It can be seen that there was no respondent who was categorized as having very low SECQ and low SECQ, there were seven respondents (10.3%) categorized as having medium SECQ, there were 43 respondents (63.2%) categorized as having high SECQ and there were 18 respondents (26.5%) categorized as having very high SECQ. It can be inferred that the majority of these pre-service teachers had more than enough social emotional competence related to be aware, to manage, to decide, and to control the emotion in any situation in the classroom, in which this could lead them to produce the effective learning process to achieve better achievements.

Table 5 presents cumulative means of the five social-emotional competencies. The lowest mean from the five social emotional competencies was social awareness ($M=14.5104$). Then, it was followed by the four other social emotional competencies, namely self-management ($M=16.0901$), relationship skill ($M=16.8709$), self-awareness ($M=16.9795$), and responsible decision making ($M=21.3269$). This result revealed that responsible decision making was the mostly acquired competence by students and how it was related to their academic achievement [22]. The pre-service teachers had high responsible decision-making skill meaning that they were able to decide something by firstly thinking and measuring any result or consequence of their decisions. When students had high responsible decision making, they were able to consider any impacts before taking the action. In relation to this study, the pre-service teachers were able to take consideration before deciding something. Meanwhile, the results of the following order of the other competencies, namely self-

awareness, relationship skill, self-management, and social awareness revealed the assumption that the pre-service teachers were able to be aware and maintain their own emotions which can also relate to the way they communicate with others especially peers for creating the relationship or network.

Table 4. The results of social emotional questionnaire (SECQ)

Interval	Category	Frequency	Percentage
22.00–38.00	Very low	0	0 %
38.01–56.00	Low	0	0 %
56.01–74.00	Medium	7	10.3 %
74.01–92.00	High	43	63.2 %
92.01–110.00	Very high	18	26.5 %

Table 5. The cumulative means of the five social-emotional competencies

Social-emotional competencies	Mean
Self-awareness	16.9795
Social awareness	14.5104
Self-management	16.0901
Relationship skills	16.8709
Responsible decision making	21.3269

Meanwhile, the minimum score of the respondents' grade point average (GPA) was 2.86, and the maximum score was 3.74. The mean of their GPA was 3.414 and the standard deviation was 0.1559. Table 6 presents the documentation of the respondents' cumulative GPA, in which none of the respondents had below 2.00 of graduate predicate of the GPA. However, there were 17 respondents (25%) got 3.51-4.00 of cum-laude predicate of GPA, 50 respondents (73.5%) had 3.10-3.50 of very satisfactory predicate of GPA, and one respondent (1.5%) had 2.76-3.00 of satisfactory predicate of GPA. It can be interpreted that most of the pre-service teachers had moderate academic achievement because they had achieved the medium GPA category with the range of 3.10-3.50. It can be inferred that they were able to understand and achieve the boundary of the result of the learning activities in the classroom. This could be affected by their ability to be aware and manage themselves in studying, including how they fulfill their responsibility and how they build good relationship with their peers and teachers. The ability of being aware of oneself and the ability of trying harder in learning could possibly give a significant performance of the students in academic performance [27].

Table 6. The results of students' level of cumulative GPA

Cumulative GPA	Predicate	Frequency	Percentage
3.51–4.00	Cum-laude	17	25%
3.10–3.50	Very Satisfactory	50	73.5%
2.76–3.00	Satisfactory	1	1.5%
≥2.00	Graduated	0	0%

3.2. The correlations: Mindfulness, social-emotional competence, and academic achievement

The correlational analysis was conducted to find out the correlation between: i) mindfulness and academic achievement; ii) social-emotional competence and academic achievement; and iii) mindfulness and social-emotional competence toward academic achievement. It includes the analysis of the correlation among each dimension of mindfulness and social-emotional competence.

First, the analysis of the correlation between the respondents' mindfulness and academic achievement shows that the r -obtained was 0.258 and the p -value was 0.033. The p -value (0.033) which was lower than the significant level (0.05) means there was a significant correlation between the pre-service teachers' mindfulness and academic achievement. However, the correlation was classified as weak because the r -obtained was (0.258). This study found that there was a significant weak correlation with positive direction. Moreover, Table 7 presents the result of each of the FFMQ dimension correlation to academic achievement. Only non-judging (0.038) was the dimension of mindfulness that correlated to the academic achievement.

It can be inferred that even though the students had high observing and describing dimension of five facet mindfulness, it did not reflect to the result of the correlation between the variables. In this study, it exactly showed that only non-judging dimension which was acquired moderately by the pre-service teachers correlated to their academic achievement. This might happen because they have applied to explore and express the process of noticing feelings and emotion to other situation or activity include or beside the learning process. When they

are able to control their emotion and feelings in learning process, it could impact to their result of the academic achievement because they tend to try doing the best by setting a side the negative thoughts, to not create any judgements toward what they result they would get, and to not disapprove themselves of whatever their ideas.

Table 7. The correlation among each dimension of mindfulness and academic achievement

Five facet mindfulness questionnaire	r-obtained (Pearson correlation)	p-value Sig (2-tailed)
Observing	0.096	0.438
Describing & describing (R)	0.142	0.247
Acting with awareness (R)	0.222	0.069
Non-judging (R)	0.253	0.038
Non-reacting	0.205	0.093

Second, the analysis of the correlation between respondents' social emotional competence and academic achievement shows that the r-obtained was (0.230) and the p-value was (0.059). This means there was no significant correlation between the pre-service teachers' social emotional competence and their academic achievement. However, Table 8 presents the result of correlation of each competency to academic achievement showing that self-management (0.018) was the only one which correlated with academic achievement. It can be assumed that the pre-service teachers were able to manage themselves during the learning process which could support them in getting improved academic achievement. While the other competencies such as self-awareness (0.844), social-awareness (0.240), relationship skill (0.904), and responsible decision making (0.109) did not correlate with academic achievement. Even though the responsible decision making was mostly acquired by the pre-service teachers, but in fact it did not significantly correlate with their academic achievement. It can be inferred that, although they had high responsible decision making in some terms such as being able to decide something by firstly thinking, measuring any results of what has been decided, and taking consideration before deciding something, those were not the aspects related to their academic achievements. This could also happen because they might be more able to decide something in doing their other daily activities which require more of their consideration than in their activity of studying.

Table 8. The Correlation among each dimension of social emotional competence and academic achievement

Social-emotional competencies	r-obtained (Pearson correlation)	p-value Sig (2-tailed)
Self-awareness	0.024	0.844
Social awareness	0.144	0.240
Self-management	0.287	0.018
Relationship skills	0.015	0.904
Responsible decision making	0.196	0.109

To determine the correlation between the pre-service teachers' mindfulness and social emotional competence toward their academic achievement, another correlation analysis was conducted as presented in Table 9. The results of the correlation between students' mindfulness and social emotional competence toward academic achievement was (0.300) for r-table, and (0.013) for p-value. There was a significant weak correlation among the pre-service teachers' mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement. It can be inferred that the higher the mindfulness and social emotional competence, the higher the academic achievement. The three variables, namely mindfulness, social emotional competence and academic achievement are related to each other. Mindfulness and social emotional competence have been proven to have benefit to pre-service teachers' academic achievement.

Table 9. The correlation between mindfulness and social emotional competence toward academic achievement

		FFMQSECQ	GPA
FFMQSECQ	Pearson correlation	1	.300*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.013
	N	68	68
GPA	Pearson correlation	.300*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.013	
	N	68	68

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

3.3. The regression analysis

Table 10 presents the result of the regression analysis between the respondents' mindfulness to their academic achievement showing that the sig. F change was (0.033). This means that mindfulness significantly influenced the academic achievement of the pre-service teachers because it (0.033) was lower than (0.05). On the other hand, the adjusted R square was (0.053). It can be inferred that mindfulness explained 5.3% variability in the academic achievement. In other words, the contribution of mindfulness to academic achievement of the pre-service teachers was 5.3%.

However, based on the correlation statistic before, the dimension which correlated to the academic achievement was non-judging. Therefore, the authors checked the contribution of non-judging dimension to the academic achievement of the respondents and found that the adjusted R square was (0.050) as seen in Table 11. This means that non-judging explained 5% of the variability in academic achievement. In other words, the contribution of non-judging to academic achievement was 5%.

Table 10. The regression analysis between mindfulness and academic achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	R Square change	Change statistics			Sig. F Change
						F Change	df1	df2	
1	.258 ^a	.067	.053	.15177	.067	4.721	1	66	.033

a. Predictors: (Constant), totalffmq

Table 11. The regression analysis between non-judging and academic achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	R Square change	Change statistics			Sig. F Change
						F Change	df1	df2	
1	.253 ^a	.064	.050	.15201	.064	4.504	1	66	.038

a. Predictors: (Constant), totalnonjudging

From the results of 5.3% contribution of mindfulness to academic achievement and 5% non-judging dimension contribution to academic achievement, it can be inferred that the pre-service teachers should try harder in applying the aspects of mindfulness to the learning activities such as being able in observing the situation to stay focus, improving the ability to describe what they felt, minimizing the negative thoughts, decreasing the negative reaction, and focusing the thoughts in learning. They had tried to learn purely and independently by putting the other judgment or perception especially negative perception in learning, so they could gain the result of learning activities without worrying too much on their own negative mindset. Then, this could lead them to get better performance to gain the better academic achievement. One of the dimensions of mindfulness which is non-judging dimension could predict inversely to students' depression, stress, anxiety, and well-being [28]. In addition, the non-judgmental aspect in mindfulness could predict the level of depression and anxiety of the students which means when the level of nonjudgmental of the students was high, the level of depression and anxiety is low [29]. It means the academic achievement can also be related to someone's depression and anxiety level.

Moreover, since there was a correlation between self-management in SECQ and academic achievement, the authors only checked the contribution of self-management to the academic achievement of the respondents. Table 12 shows the adjusted R square was 0.068. This means that self-management explained 6.8% of the variability in academic achievement. In other words, the contribution of self-management to academic achievement was 6.8%. This small contribution means that the pre-service teachers were still able to manage themselves in terms of learning, such as managing the schedules, managing to stay focused in the learning process, and managing themselves to control their emotion in learning, in which the academic self-management which relates to motivational and behavioral, learning, and study strategies is really needed to maintain the factors that could affect the result of the learning process to the learning process [30].

The result of the regression analysis between mindfulness, social emotional competence and academic achievement in Table 13 shows that the adjusted R square was 0.076. This means that respondents' mindfulness and social emotional competence explained 7.6% of the variability in academic achievement. In other words, the contribution of the pre-service teachers' mindfulness and social emotional competence to their academic achievement was 7.6%, which was considered low.

Table 12. The regression analysis between self-management and academic achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	R Square change	Change statistics			Sig. F Change
						F Change	df1	df2	
1	.287 ^a	.082	.068	.15052	.082	5.903	1	66	.018

a. Predictors: (Constant), selfmanagement

Table 13. The regression analysis between mindfulness and social-emotional competence toward academic achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	R Square change	Change statistics			Sig. F Change
						F Change	df1	df2	
1	.300 ^a	.090	.076	.14989	.090	6.513	1	66	.013

a. Predictors: (Constant), ffmqsecq

However, it can be inferred that there was still contribution from both mindfulness and social emotional competence toward academic achievement. Even though there was still little contribution, it could not be neglected. The contribution of mindfulness was mostly gained by the ability of the pre-service teachers to stay positive and do the best for their learning process, so their academic achievement increased. On the other hand, their ability to manage themselves in terms of overcoming stressful situation, overcoming anxiety, and staying calm in the new changing situation also become the reasons why they gained academic achievements. The set of the knowledge of mindfulness for an individual as the beginning teacher would help to decrease the level of stress, and manage the pedagogical ability in terms of being mindful in learning to boost the effective learning process [12]. The pre-service teachers just need to utilize the use of mindfulness and social emotional competence as the factors to increase their academic achievement.

One of the indicators for the development of good education is based on the quality of the teachers. All the useful aspects in mindfulness and social emotional competence that can contribute to the academic achievement of the pre-service teachers are assumed to be supportive elements to prepare the pre-service teachers in their real journey of being professional qualified teachers in the future.

4. CONCLUSION

This study highlighted the weak significant correlation among the pre-service teachers' mindfulness, social-emotional competence and academic achievement. From all five facet mindfulness' dimensions and social emotional competence, there was only one in each dimension and competency that correlated to academic achievement. In five facet mindfulness dimensions, only non-judging dimension correlated to academic achievement, and in social emotional competence, only self-management correlated to academic achievement. There was little contribution from both mindfulness and social competence toward academic achievement. The contribution of mindfulness was mostly gained by the ability of the pre-service teachers to stay positive and do the best for their learning process, so their academic achievement increased. The pre-service teachers' mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement indeed have relationship one another. Their mindfulness and social emotional competence have been proven to be beneficial to support the pre-service teachers' academic achievement.

This study only serves as the initial study on the topic of mindfulness, social emotional competence, and academic achievement in Indonesian educational context. It is hoped that more people working in the field of education can be more aware about the importance of mindfulness and social emotional competence for improving ones' academic achievements. Mindfulness and social emotional based instructions are suggested to be integrated into the teaching and learning discourse in the classroom because it is necessary to balance the learning process along with the mindfulness and social emotional competence of the teachers and students.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Kamlesh, "Role of teacher in quality education," *International Journal of English Language, Literature and Humanities*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp. 226-233, 2015.
- [2] K. Selvi, "Teacher's competencies," *International Journal of Philosophy of Culture and Axiologi*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 167-175, 2016, doi: 10.5840/cultura20107133.
- [3] A. Bhargava and M. Pathy, "Perception of student teachers about teaching competencies," *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, vol. 1, no.1, pp. 77-81, 2011.
- [4] P. Pahrudin, T. Martono, and W. Murtini "The effect of pedagogic competency, personality, professional and social competency teacher to study achievement of economic lesson in state senior high school of East Lombok district academic year 2015/2016," in *Proceeding the 2nd International Conference on Teacher Training and Education Sebelas Maret University*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2016, pp. 332-245.
- [5] P. A. Jennings and M. T. Greenberg, "The prosocial classroom: Teacher social emotional competence in relation to student classroom outcomes," *Review of Educational Research*, vol. 79, no. 1, pp. 491-525, 2009.

- [6] R. J. Marzano, J. S. Marzano, and D. J. Pickering, *Classroom Management That Works: Research-Based Strategies for Every Teacher*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development, 2003.
- [7] K. A. Schonert-Reichl and M. S. Lawlor, "The effects of a mindfulness-based education program on pre- and early adolescents' well-being and social and emotional competence," *Mindfulness*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 137–151, 2010.
- [8] C. Davenport and F. Pagnini, "Mindful learning: A case study of langerian mindfulness in schools," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 7, no. 1372, pp. 1–5, 2016.
- [9] R. A. Baer, G. T. Smith, J. Hopkins, J. Krietemeyer, and L. Toney, "Using self-report assessment methods to explore facets of mindfulness," *Assessment*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 27–45, 2006.
- [10] E. Dorman, "Building teachers' social-emotional competence through mindfulness practices," *Curriculum and Teaching Dialogue*, vol. 17, no. 1-2, pp. 103-119, 2015.
- [11] N. J. Albrecht, P. M. Albrecht, and M. Cohen, "Mindfully teaching in the classroom: A literature review," *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, vol. 37, no. 12, pp. 1-14, 2012, doi: 10.14221/ajte.2012v37n12.2.
- [12] R. S. Bernay and R. Bernay, "Mindfulness and the beginning teacher," *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 58-69, 2014.
- [13] A. Nesayan, B. Hosseini, and R. A. Gandomani, "The effectiveness of emotion regulation skills training on anxiety and emotional regulation strategies in adolescent students," *Journal of Practice in Clinical Psychology*, vol. 5, no.4, pp. 263–270, 2017, doi: 10.29252/nirp.jpcp.5.4.263.
- [14] S. L. Kerr, *et al.*, "Is mindfulness training useful for pre-service teachers? An exploratory investigation," *Teaching Education*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 349-359, 2017, doi: 10.1080/10476210.2017.1296831.
- [15] B. Y. Illahi and H. Khandai, "Social intelligence, study habits and academic achievements of college students of District Pulwama," *Journal of Education and Practice*, vol. 6, no. 23, pp. 76–82, 2016.
- [16] A. Riswanto and S. Aryani, "Learning motivation and student achievement: Description analysis and relationship," *The International Journal of Counseling and Education*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 42-47, 2017.
- [17] T. T. York, C. Gibson, and S. Rankin, "Defining and measuring academic success," *Practical Assessment, Research and Evaluation*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 1–20, 2015.
- [18] P. J. Kpolovie, A. I. Joe, and T. Okoto "Academic achievement prediction: Role of interest in learning and attitude towards school," *International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education*, vol. 1, no. 11, pp. 73-100, 2014.
- [19] K. Teodorczuk, "Mindfulness and academic achievement in South African university student," Bachelor's Degree, University of Johannesburg, South Africa, 2016, doi: 10.13140/RG.2.1.3307.8169.
- [20] S. Lu, C.-C. Huang, and J. Rios, "Mindfulness and academic performance: an example of migrant children in China," *Children and Youth Services Review*, vol. 82, no. 32, pp. 53-59, 2017.
- [21] D. C. Mocerri, "The assessment of students' social and emotional competencies and academic achievement," Doctoral Dissertation, The State University of New Jersey, New Brunswick, Canada, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://rucore.libraries.rutgers.edu/rutgers-lib/48613/PDF/1/play>.
- [22] G. Wirajaya, L. A. Suganda, and Z. Zuraida "Indonesian students' social-emotional competencies and their English academic achievement," *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 163–169, 2019.
- [23] K. Bertolini, A. Stremmel, and J. Thorngren, "Student Achievement Factors," 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED568687.pdf>.
- [24] M. Zhou and J. Ee, "Development and Validation of the Social Emotional Competence Questionnaire (SECQ)," *The International Journal of Emotional Education*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 27–42, 2012.
- [25] E. Rosenstreich and M. Margalit, "Loneliness, Mindfulness, and Academic Achievements: A Moderation Effect among First-Year College Students," *The Open Psychology Journal*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 138–145, 2015.
- [26] E. M. Vonderheyde, "The relationship between mindfulness and stress among college students," Theses and Dissertations, Rowan University, United States, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://rdw.rowan.edu/etd/2431>.
- [27] U. S. David and U. Okon, "Influence of Self and Social Awareness on Business Education Students' Academic Performance in Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria," *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 1-8, 2016.
- [28] C. K. Soysa and C. J. Wilcomb, "Mindfulness, Self-compassion, Self-efficacy, and Gender as Predictors of Depression, Anxiety, Stress, and Well-being," *Mindfulness*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 217–226, 2015.
- [29] M. Cash and K. Whittingham, "What Facets of Mindfulness Contribute to Psychological Well-Being and Depressive, Anxious, and Stress-Related Symptomatology?" *Mindfulness*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 177–182, 2010.
- [30] A. L. Kadiyono and H. Hafiar, "The role of academic self-management in improving students' academic achievement," in *Ideas for 21st Century Education*. Routledge, 2017.